

TYPES OF LESSON ANALYSIS

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This article talks about the types of lesson analysis, their content and their meaning. Young teachers are exposed to learning and seeing different methods of analyzing lessons .

Key words: Scientific, psychological, method, didactic, practical, biological, botanical, anatomical-morphological , ecological.

Lesson analysis can be divided into five large groups according to their nature :

1. Scientific analysis.
2. Psychological analysis.
3. Methodological analysis.
4. Didactic analysis.
5. General pedagogical analysis.

Now we will consider each of them separately.

1. Scientific analysis

In this analysis, the scientific-theoretical correctness and perfection of the knowledge given to the students, as well as the perfection of the independent work performed by the students and its direction towards the specific goal, are determined based on the characteristics of the educational subject. The characteristics of educational subjects are fully revealed in the analysis of lessons.

In the scientific analysis of the lesson, it is necessary to pay attention to the following :

- a) correct description and correct display of rules and definitions, numbers;
 - b) the teacher's scientific approach to the topic;
 - c) to their understanding of the history of science,
 - g) teacher's conclusions, final results, their scientific correctness, perfection
 - d) enrichment of textbook materials with additional literary materials, appropriateness of laboratory and independent work performed by students ;
- taking into account the specific requirements of the educational subject ;
- when the analyst talks about issues that are not relevant to the lesson being analyzed, and does not express his opinion clearly about the important aspects of the lesson.

However, "Scientific-pedagogical clarification of educational content means political and epistemological opinion from a pedagogical point of view. Any pedagogical theory, pedagogical system is an expression of a methodological position.

" In order to correctly solve the content of education, it is necessary to study these historical experiences "

1. Analyzing the lesson from a scientific point of view requires a brief introduction to the history of science and biographies of scientists related to the subject. In the scientific analysis of the lessons, it is important to determine the scientific conclusions made by the teacher regarding the knowledge he is imparting and the compatibility of these scientific conclusions with the students' level of knowledge, and their participation in drawing conclusions.

students without developing skills about the ways and methods of studying science. For example, students not only observe physical and chemical phenomena during experiments, but also perform laboratory and various practical work. With this, their initial scientific research begins. Naturally, the students are

asked "does scientific research lead to certain results?" the question is interesting. They will find an answer to this question by acquiring information about the history of the subject (science).

The history of science is a particularly important part of knowledge. He interprets when the knowledge taught at school came about, when it started to be studied. Accordingly, students should have a clear idea of the history of science. For example, when teaching the topic "Magnetism" (physics class) in the 9th grade, most teachers refer to the history of science. Scientists who have discovered news related to "magnetism" remind us of its civic and moral qualities: principledness, self-criticism, fairness, demandingness. Therefore, checking the students' knowledge is only of a control nature. rather, it should serve to increase their interest in reading and science, and to train their thinking ability. The rule, the correct description of the definitions and the scientific attitude of the teacher to the topic are analyzed in a coherent unit. In this type of analysis, scientific sources and opinions of experts related to the taught subject are used. Below we give examples from the opinions of specialists in geography, botany, grammar of the Uzbek language. The following are taken into account when analyzing lessons related to the subject of geography from a scientific point of view:

- a) study and observe the local characteristics of the pr e dmet ;
- b) comparing the geographical features of the place where he was born and raised with the geographical features of other places;
- c) taking into account that the study of geography depends on the excursion;
- g) use of the card;
- d) full use of numerical indicators.

In terms of the system of knowledge given to students in botany, botany classes are divided into five types:

1. Anatomical-morphological lessons.
2. Physiological lessons.

3. Lessons of ecological character.
4. Lessons on systematics.
5. Lessons of a biological and agrotechnical nature

Lessons devoted to the study of the Uzbek language include:

1. To teach students to use speech sounds, syllables, and words appropriately when composing sentences, and to write them correctly.

2. Enriching students' speech with various words and syntactic constructions and teaching them to compose speech through them.

3. Educate students intellectually, aesthetically, ethically and form a materialistic worldview in them.

4. Preparation for continuing education after the eighth grade

In the scientific analysis of the lesson, the above-mentioned inseparable tasks of each educational subject are fully taken into account. Because the definition or rule explained by the teacher seems like a scientific prediction for the student. Scientific prediction is based on the introduction of the laws of nature and society in the field of its unknown and yet to occur phenomena. "The criterion of the correctness of scientific predictions is always practice"

2. Psychological analysis

Various psychological demands are placed on the teacher analyzing the lesson. The analyst of the lesson gives importance to the teacher's training of the student's abilities during the lesson, the methods he used to create and develop volitional activity, and how the student reacted to the imaginative activity considered necessary for imagination and creativity. Psychological analysis is characterized by the study of the ability, interest, temperament, character traits, perception, attention of the student and the teacher. Psychological analysis differs from other types of lesson analysis in its complexity. This complexity requires the teacher to study psychology independently. Due to the complexity of

psychological analysis, although scientific staff, expert psychologists, well-versed methodical teachers are engaged in psychological analysis of lessons, the involvement of the public in this work plays an important role in improving the quality of education. The psychological analyst examines the activity of the teacher and the student in the lesson based on the improved psychological foundations of education . That is, he studies the teacher's reliance on the psychological foundations of education during the course of the lesson, the behavioral and psychological conditions of the students during their academic work and the course of the lesson. In the study of method, temperament and character, the analysts of classes use psychological methods and are based on the methods of materialistic worldview. Because the principled approach to psychological research is determined by the requirements of the analytical method. The dialectical method requires the study of each mental phenomenon and all the other things connected with it in relation to the phenomena and their interrelationship. The lesson is analyzed based on the concept of personality, psychological methods, the method of observation (external observation, self-observation), the method of checking the effectiveness of activity . Psychological methods are used to study character and temperament. Psychological analysis examines the character traits of a person on the example of students and teachers.

In this case, the following features of the teacher 's attitude are evaluated:

- a) characteristics that express their relationship to the collective of students and individual students;
- b) characteristics expressing the attitude to the teaching profession;
- c) characteristics expressing the relationship to things;
- g) characteristics that express the attitude of the teacher to himself.

Analyzing these relations from a psychological point of view, the teacher of the lesson either approves of these characteristics or demands to change them. For example, the analyst psychologically analyzes the teacher's consideration of the

student's character and temperament when he is overexposed, or when he is responding to the teacher, or when he is doing independent work, and the pedagogical method used by the teacher in the same process, and this determines which methods are appropriate or inappropriate. Such an analysis will help pedagogues in studying the perception of students; will give. Analyzing perception and attention, while the teacher is explaining some material to the students, how they absorb this material, how they perceive it, how they remember it, how they think, how attention and emotions are manifested in them. and how this process is changing them. Therefore, the study of the influence of the teacher on the students' perception of knowledge is of particular importance in psychological analysis. An excellent analysis of the perception of knowledge: to do,

first of all, the process of perception, the teacher's statement in this process (methods of influence, slow or speed of his statement) are thoroughly studied. Because students perceive knowledge in different processes and from different perspectives .

For example:

1. In the teacher's oral story.
2. In the conversation.
3. In the lecture.
4. Movies, educational films, slide films.
5. Demonstration of weapons with television instructions.
6. During the excursions.
7. When teaching based on textbooks and various manuals.
8. In the process of doing independent work.

In the analysis, the attention of students in the process of perception is studied, and the quality of their perception is determined by the quality of their

perception and the level of meeting the requirements of the state educational program. As you know, attention is the act of focusing and concentrating on one point, an event, an object that is perceiving, imagining. Therefore, the attention of the student analyzing the lesson observes, examines and analyzes involuntary and voluntary types. Content, effective concrete-objective factors impose psychological demands on the lesson and the student (based on objective factors). That is why, while observing the student during the lesson, the teacher studies deeply whether he can force himself to sit in a certain position, to listen to the teacher's speech consistently, or to study independently. Therefore, when studying attention:

- a) the student's ability to shift his attention from one lesson to another;
- b) the ability to shift attention from listening to the teacher's words to the answer;
- c) the ability to pass from reading to speaking is checked.

In the analysis of attention, it is taken into account that when solving a complex problem, the student concentrates his attention only on solving the problem (he may not even hear the ghost, the sounds). The reasons for the concentration and distribution of attention are recorded in the "Lesson analysis notebook".

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